

SOILHEALTH1: SOIL HEALTH: CURRENT STATUS AND FUTURE NEEDS

PROGRAM AUTHORS KEYWORDS

PROGRAM

Days: [Monday, October 7th](#) [Tuesday, October 8th](#)
[Wednesday, October 9th](#)

Monday, October 7th

View this program: [with abstracts](#) [session overview](#) [talk overview](#)

08:45-09:15 Session RD: Registration

LOCATION: [Registration Desk Aristotle](#)

09:15-09:30 Session S0: Opening SoilHealth 2024

CHAIR: [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

09:30-11:00 Session PS1: Plenary 1

CHAIRS:

[Thomas Reitz](#), [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#) and [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

09:30 [Mirco Barbero](#)

Towards a Directive on soil (abstract)

10:15 [Carlos Guerra](#)

New frontiers in soil health knowledge (abstract)

11:00-11:30 ☕ Coffee Break

11:30-13:45 Session PS2: Plenary 2

CHAIRS:

[Thomas Reitz](#), [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#) and [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

11:30 [Panos Panagos](#)

The Role of EU Soil Observatory in improving soil health of the EU (abstract)

12:15 [Jenni Dungait](#)

Trends in soil health monitoring (abstract)

13:00 [Luis Sanchez Alvarez](#)

A Soil Deal for Europe': leading the transition towards healthy soils (abstract)

13:45-14:30 🍴 Lunch Break

Méditerranée Restaurant

14:30-16:30 Session S1: Soil organic C monitoring and Biogeochemical modeling

CHAIRS: [Nikolaos C Vavlas](#) and [Manuel Mayr](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

14:30 [Manuel Mayr](#), [Ludvig Forslund](#), [Nadine Gobron](#), [Andreas Brink](#), [Usue Donezar](#) and [Rainer Baritz](#)
Copernicus Land Monitoring Service – land datasets in support of soil health and soil monitoring ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Manuel Mayr](#)

14:50 [Nikolaos C Vavlas](#), [Lammert Kooistra](#) and [Gerlinde De Deyn](#)

Soil Health Monitoring by Integrating UAV data and soil-crop modelling ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nikolaos C Vavlas](#)

15:10 [Konstantinos Vasileios Karyotis](#), [Cecilie Hermansen](#) and [George Zalidis](#)

Harmonizing Soil Spectral Libraries: Enhancing Modeling Performance for Soil Organic Carbon Estimation in Greek Croplands ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Konstantinos Vasileios Karyotis](#)

15:30 [Evangelia Koukianaki](#), [Maria Lilli](#) and [Nikolaos Nikolaidis](#)

Modeling carbon sequestration of an avocado plantation ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Evangelia Koukianaki](#)

15:50 [Mohammad Ibrahim Khalil](#) and [M.I. Khalil](#)

HOLOS-IE Model for Farm-C Footprint and Integration Potential of Soil Health and Ecosystem Services ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [M.I. Khalil](#)

16:10 [Evangelia Koukianaki](#), [Maria Lilli](#) and [Nikolaos Nikolaidis](#)

Forested ecosystem modeling using the 1D-ICZ model ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Evangelia Koukianaki](#)

16:30-17:00 ☕ Coffee Break

17:00-19:00 Session S2: Management of Nitrogen and N₂O emissions in agroecosystems

CHAIRS: [Eleftherios Evangelou](#) and [Peter Dörsch](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

17:00 [Antonios Apostolakis](#), [Paulina Englert](#), [Oliver L. Daka](#), [Stefan Siebert](#) and [Ana Meijide](#)

Crop yield, soil carbon storage and nitrous oxide emissions under long-term reduced tillage and controlled drought conditions ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Antonios Apostolakis](#)

17:20 [Eleftherios Evangelou](#)

Canopy reflectance guides variable-rate nitrogen fertilization and infers spatial variability in soil fertility ([abstract](#))

17:40 [Sigrid Trier Kjær](#), [Rong Lang](#) and [Peter Dörsch](#)

Balancing off-season nitrous oxide emissions and potential carbon sequestration by cover crops in hemiboreal cereal production ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Sigrid Trier Kjær](#)

18:00 [Georgios Papaioannou](#), [Eirini Vasarmidi](#), [Myrto](#)

[Tsiknia](#), [Vasileios Tzanakakis](#) and [Konstantinos Ehaliotis](#)

Effects of soil salinity on nitrification in six different soils with distinct characteristics and management history ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Vasileios Tzanakakis](#)

18:20 [Nikolaos Paranychanakis](#), [Safiye Tul](#) and [Maria Frantzeskou](#)

Non-tillage stimulates short-lived emissions of N₂O during the re-wetting of soils ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nikolaos Paranychanakis](#)

19:00-22:30 || Gala Dinner

Méditerranée Restaurant

Tuesday, October 8th

View this program: [with abstracts](#) [session overview](#) [talk overview](#)

09:00-11:00 Session S3: Soil Health Status and Restoration

CHAIRS: [Marie Muehe](#) and [Nicholaos Danalatos](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

09:00 [Nikos Nikolaidis](#)

Towards Integrated Water and Land Management: The Water-Ecosystem-Food Nexus and Nature-Based Solutions ([abstract](#))

09:45 [Dimitrios Bartzialis](#), [Gerasimos J. Danalatos](#), [Ippolytos Gintsioudis](#), [Kyriakos Giannoulis](#) and [Nikolaos Danalatos](#)

Long Term Impacts of Land Use (Annual vs. Perennial Crops) and Sustainable Land Management Practices on Soil Quality Indices in Vulnerable Mediterranean Agroecosystems ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nikolaos Danalatos](#)

10:05 [Katharina Pronkow](#), [Josephine Bukowiecki](#), [Nora Honsdorf](#) and [Henning Kage](#)

Crop Rotational Position Influences Soil Water Uptake and Canopy Temperature in Winter Wheat ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Katharina Pronkow](#)

10:25 [Christos Vasilikiotis](#), [Alice Chidiac](#), [Iraklis Roulias](#), [Sarah Meis](#), [John Woodruff](#) and [Andreas Efstathiou](#)

Integrating Multi-Species Cover Crops with Organic No-Till Practices for Enhanced Soil Health and Quality ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Christos Vasilikiotis](#)

10:45 [Thomas Reitz](#), [Lena Philipp](#), [Alice Calvo](#), [Fabiano Sillo](#), [Luis Daniel Prada Salcedo](#), [Vincenzo Montesano](#), [Mauro Centritto](#) and [Raffaella Balestrini](#)

Climate Change Impact on Agronomic Plant Parameters and the Associated Soil Microbiome in Agricultural Systems of Germany and Italy ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Thomas Reitz](#)

11:05-11:30 ☕ Coffee Break

11:30-13:30 Session S4: Soil Health Status and Restoration

CHAIRS: [Christos Vasilikiotis](#) and [Vasileios Tzanakakis](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

- 11:30 [Konstantinos Zoukidis](#), [Christos Vasilikiotis](#), [Athanasios Gertsis](#), [Antonio Scialletti](#), [Georgios Strouthopoulos](#) and [Evangelos Vergos](#)
Effect of an organo-mineral fertilizer produced by recovered sulphur & orange wastes on winter wheat growth as a sustainable mitigation of soil desertification ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Konstantinos Zoukidis](#)
- 11:50 [Dimitrios Triantakonstantis](#), [Maria Batsalia](#) and [Nikolaos Lolos](#)
Topsoil and subsoil distribution of soil properties in an agricultural area ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Maria Batsalia](#)
- 12:10 [Konstantinos Zoukidis](#), [Athanasios Gertsis](#), [Stefanos Stefanou](#), [Vasileios-Marios Stathopoulos](#), [Pavlos Prantzios](#), [Georgios Strouthopoulos](#) and [Ramonna Kosheleva](#)
Irrigation with high salinity water using innovative technologies (nanobubbles and an electronic water treatment system) to evaluate lettuce production grown in pots in greenhouse ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Konstantinos Zoukidis](#)
- 12:30 [Ioannis Zografakis](#), [Konstantina Skalidi](#), [Elena Stavridou](#), [Despoina Pediaditaki](#), [Symeon Papanikolaou](#), [Georgios Papaioannou](#), [Ioannis Spyridakis](#), [Ioannis Chasourakis](#), [Antonios Loulakis](#), [Nikolaos Volakakis](#), [Vasileios Tzanakakis](#) and [Emmanouil Kambourakis](#)
The effect of management system and agroecological zone on soil organic matter and microbial activity of olive orchards in Crete, Greece ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Ioannis Zografakis](#)
- 12:50 [Athanasios Gertsis](#), [Evangelos Vergos](#), [Konstantinos Zoukidis](#) and [Stefanos Stefanou](#)
Agronomic responses to biochar application rates of leafy vegetables grown in pots under greenhouse conditions filled with two soils and two inert hydroponic substrates ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Athanasios Gertsis](#)
- 13:10 [Alexandros Stefanakis](#)
A circular management model of waste sources reuse and recycling in the oil industry using nature-based solutions: case study in the Middle East ([abstract](#))

13:30-14:00 Session PS: Poster Session

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

- 13:30 [Antonios Apostolakis](#), [Nikolaos P. Nikolaidis](#) and [Nikolaos V. Paranychanakis](#)
Gradual recovery of soil structure and organic carbon stocks in semi-arid fine-textured soils

- after setting aside arable land ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Antonios Apostolakis](#)
- 13:33 [Manolis Grillakis](#), [Athanasios Tsilimigkras](#) and [Aristeidis Koutroulis](#)
Climate change impacts on the rainfall erosivity for the Mediterranean ([abstract](#))
- 13:36 [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#), [Maria Frantzeskou](#), [Safiye Tul](#) and [Nefeli Milaiou](#)
Response of soil microbial communities to olive mill wastewater application ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#)
- 13:39 [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#) and [Maria Frantzeskou](#)
Strong compositional shifts in leaf microbiome precede the development of leaf abscission zone and form litter decomposing communities ([abstract](#))
- 13:42 [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#), [Safiye Tul](#), [Maria Frantzeskou](#) and [Thomas Reitz](#)
Soil microbial communities respond slowly to soil conservation practices in the Mediterranean region ([abstract](#))
- 13:45 [Safiye Tul](#), [Maria Frantzeskou](#) and [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#)
Climate-driven variability in soil Enzyme dynamics: Unveiling temperature sensitivity of phosphatase and β -glucosidase activity ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Safiye Tul](#)
- 13:48 [Nektarios Kavroulakis](#), [Myrto Tsiknia](#), [Maria Kissandraki](#), [Constantinos Chrysikopoulos](#) and [Anastasios Malandrakis](#)
Assessing the Ecotoxicological Impact of Metallic Nanoparticles on Soil Microbial Community Structures ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Anastasios Malandrakis](#)
- 13:51 [Ioanna Manolikaki](#), [Georgios Koubouris](#), [Dimitrios Voloudakis](#), [Ioannis Kapsomenakis](#), [Themistoklis Koutsouras](#), [George Koutras](#), [Anna Vlachou](#) and [Georgios Motakis](#)
Digital Tools And Early Warning System For The Adaptation Of Olive Production To Climate Change - Olivealarm ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Georgios Koubouris](#)
- 13:54 [Andreas Angelakis](#) and [Vasileios Tzanakakis](#)
Evolution of Water and Health in Greece ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Vasileios Tzanakakis](#)
- 13:57 [Ioannis Kasapakis](#), [Androniki Papafilippaki](#), [Andreas Mavredakis](#), [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#) and [Konstantinos Chartzoulakis](#)
Agricultural soil health assessment with DSS combining open data and crop management information. ([abstract](#))
 PRESENTER: [Ioannis Kasapakis](#)

14:00-15:00 || Lunch Break

Méditerranée Restaurant

15:00-17:00 Session S5: Soil Microbiota and

functioning: Response to management practices and environmental factors

CHAIRS: [Thomas Reitz](#) and [Myrto Tsiknia](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

15:00 [Lena Philipp](#), [Mengqi Wu](#), [Evgenia Blagodatskaya](#) and [Thomas Reitz](#)
Soil Microbial Communities in Croplands and Grasslands: The Role of Depth and Climate Variability ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Lena Philipp](#)

15:20 [Ana Alexandre](#), [Joana Amaro Ribeiro](#), [Francisca Morais](#) and [Isabel Brito](#)
Impact of cover crops on tomato rhizospheric microbiome ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Ana Alexandre](#)

15:40 [Georgios Leventis](#), [Dimitra Stathopoulou](#), [Martha Apostolidou](#), [Georgios Petrakis](#), [Myrto Tsiknia](#) and [Constantinos Ehaliotis](#)
Indigenous and plant specific microbial community consortia derived from phryganic biomes improve plant fitness and soil functions in ecosystem restoration of quarry deposits in Milos (Greece) ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Georgios Leventis](#)

16:00 [Savvas Paragkamian](#), [Panagiotis Sarris](#), [Evangelos Pafilis](#), [Georgios Kotoulas](#) and [Christos Christakis](#)

From microbes to ecosystems: towards a Crete island soil system ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Savvas Paragkamian](#)

16:20 [Maria Frantzeskou](#), [Rafaila Nikola Mourgela](#), [Evdokia Syranidou](#) and [Nikolaos Paranychanakis](#)
Contribution of thermotolerant bacteria on soil carbon cycle ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Maria Frantzeskou](#)

16:40 [María Teresa Salido](#), [Ana González Robles](#), [Kiriaki Varikou](#), [Antonios Nikolakakis](#), [Vasiliki Chatziieremia](#), [Ioanna Manolikaki](#), [Lea-Melissanthi Ventoura](#), [Spyros Liapakis](#), [Konstantinos Tzerakis](#), [Theodoros Aggelioudakis](#), [Panagiotis Petrakis](#), [Panagiotis Koulelis](#), [Alexandra Solomou](#), [Evangelia Avramidou](#), [Georgios Vasilakis](#), [Sotiris Theodorakopoulos](#), [Vasileios Gkisakis](#), [Asimoula Kardimaki](#), [Rubén Tarifa](#), [Pedro Rey](#), [Francisco Valera](#) and [Georgios Koubouris](#)

Olivares Vivos- Biodiversity As Added Value In Agriculture. From Ecosystem Services To Commercial Differentiation In The Case Of Greece ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Vasiliki Chatziieremia](#)

17:00-17:30 ☕ Coffee Break

17:30-19:30 Session S6: Soil Microbiome Applications: Soil health restoration and/or plant growth promotion

CHAIRS: [Ana Alexandre](#) and [Ehaliotis Constantinos](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

17:30 [Panos Moschou](#)

Paths affecting root paths ([abstract](#))

18:15 [Nikolaos Kaloterakis](#), [Andrea Braun-Kiewnick](#), [Adriana Giongo](#), [Mehdi Rashtbari](#), [Bahar S. Razavi](#), [Doreen Babin](#), [Kornelia Smalla](#), [Rüdiger Reichel](#) and [Nicolas Brüggemann](#)

Can the application of plant growth promoting *Bacillus pumilus* alleviate the early growth reduction in successively grown winter wheat? ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nikolaos Kaloterakis](#)

18:35 [Myrto Tsiknia](#), [Georgios Leventis](#), [Dimitra Stathopoulou](#), [Cleopatra Gareizou](#), [Georgios Petrakis](#) and [Constantinos Ehaliotis](#)

Ecosystem and biodiversity restoration of degraded landscapes in dry-land conditions, novel tools and practices: the case study of quarries restoration in Milos island ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Myrto Tsiknia](#)

18:55 [Simon Lewin](#), [Niklas Plag](#), [Carolina Leoni](#) and [Doreen Babin](#)

Multiphasic approach to identify efficient bacterial inoculants to support soil and crop health under field conditions ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Simon Lewin](#)

19:15 [Christina Nikolaou](#), [Myrto Tsiknia](#), [Antonios Apostolakis](#), [Dionisios Gasparatos](#) and [Constantinos Ehaliotis](#)

Linkages between the Acemannan concentration and the Composition of Plant-Associated Microbial Communities in *Aloe vera* (*Aloe Barbadensis* Miller) under increased soil salinity ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Christina Nikolaou](#)

Wednesday, October 9th

View this program: [with abstracts](#) [session overview](#) [talk overview](#)

09:00-11:00 Session S7: Organic ammendments as a mean to improve soil health and resilience of crops to pollutants

CHAIRS: [Kostas Komnitsas](#) and [Antonios Apostolakis](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

09:00 [Georgios Bartzas](#), [Maria Doula](#) and [Konstantinos Komnitsas](#)

Assessing the environmental impacts of agricultural products at farm level using an integrated life cycle assessment methodology ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Konstantinos Komnitsas](#)

09:20 [E. Marie Muehe](#), [Aleksandra Pienkowska](#), [Natalia Sánchez](#), [Ines Merbach](#), [Martin Herzberg](#), [Luis Daniel Prada Salcedo](#), [Thomas Reitz](#), [Mika Tarkka](#) and [Jill Bachelder](#)

Climate change induced accumulation of cadmium in spinach leaves can be mitigated by organic ammendments ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [E. Marie Muehe](#)

- 09:40 [Dimitra Vathi](#), [Anna Kritikaki](#), [Vasiliki Karmali](#) and [Kostas Komnitsas](#)
Effect of biochar addition on phytotoxicity reduction in Cu-contaminated soils ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Kostas Komnitsas](#)
- 10:00 [Jill Bachelder](#), [Ines Merbach](#), [Jan Michael Kaesler](#) and [Marie Muehe](#)
The effect of future change conditions on metal concentrations in wheat grains ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Jill Bachelder](#)
- 10:20 [Ioannis Asimakoulas](#), [Panagiotis Regouzas](#), [Elisavet Koukouraki](#), [Steen Nielsen](#) and [Alexandros Stefanakis](#)
Circular management of sewage sludge using sludge treatment reed beds and composting ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Ioannis Asimakoulas](#)
- 10:40 [Panagiotis Regkouzas](#), [Ioannis Asimakoulas](#), [Eirini Athanasiadou](#), [Elisavet Koukouraki](#) and [Alexandros Stefanakis](#)
Agronomic application of biochar derived from Constructed Wetland biomass and sewage sludge for the cultivation of tomatoes (*Solanum Lycopersicum*) ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Panagiotis Regkouzas](#)

11:00-11:30 ☕ Coffee Break

11:30-13:10 Session S8: Science and Policy integration: Management of soils in a changing world

CHAIRS: [Stelios Rozakis](#) and [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

- 11:30 [Stelios Rozakis](#), [Aleksandra Król-Badziak](#) and [Elzbieta Kubińska](#)
Positive multicriteria models to support policy makers for sustainability in agriculture ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Stelios Rozakis](#)
- 11:50 [Aya Khamassj](#), [M^a Helena Guimarães](#), [Fraj Chemak](#), [Amélie Bourceret](#) and [Mélanie Requier Desjardins](#)
Challenges of soil health restoration in Tunisian cereal production systems: an analysis through the Social-Ecological Systems Framework (SES) ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Aya Khamassj](#)
- 12:10 [Tiago Oliveira](#), [M^a Helena Guimarães](#), [Catarina Isidoro](#), [Stelios Rozakis](#), [Thomas Reitz](#) and [Nikolaos Paranychianakis](#)
Durum Wheat Production in Italy – Challenges and Options to Improve Soil Health ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)
- 12:30 [Stelios Rozakis](#), [Eleni Androulidaki](#), [Kostas Chartzoulakis](#) and [Nikos Paranychianakis](#)
Comparative assessment of soil management options in Cretan olive groves ([abstract](#))
PRESENTER: [Stelios Rozakis](#)
- 12:50 [Theodoros Daglis](#), [Georgios Tsironis](#), [Maria](#)

[Bakatsaki](#) and [Konstantinos P. Tsagarakis](#)

Soil Health Research Topics ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Maria Bakatsaki](#)

13:10-13:30 Session S9: Closing of Conference
SoilHealth 2024

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

13:30-14:30 || Lunch Break

Méditerranée Restaurant

14:30-16:00 Session WKSP: Workshop "Soil health:
Knowledge Gaps and future challenges"

CHAIRS:

[Nikolaos Stathopoulos](#) and [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)

LOCATION: [Amphitheater Aristotle](#)

14:30 [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)

**Preliminary assessment of the knowledge
gaps to prevent soil erosion** ([abstract](#))

14:50 [Melpomeni Zoka](#), [Nikolaos Stathopoulos](#),
[Salvador Llado](#) and [Charalampos Kontoes](#)

**Presenting the "Soils for Europe" (SOLO)
Land Degradation Think Tank** ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Melpomeni Zoka](#)

15:10 [Diana Simoes Vieira](#)

**European soil ERosion field measurements at
Plot scale** ([abstract](#))

15:30 [Nikolaos Stathopoulos](#) and [M^a Helena Guimarães](#)

**Discussion on "Soil health: Knowledge Gaps
and future challenges"** ([abstract](#))

PRESENTER: [Nikolaos Stathopoulos](#)